

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**EMERGENT MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS WITH ACUTE
CORONARY SYNDROME**

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Abstract:

Introduction: Unstable angina (UA), non-ST segment elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) and ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), are all different forms of myocardial ischemia, and are included in the term: Acute coronary syndrome (ACS). Nearly 1.3 million of hospital admissions in the US per year are for ACS. The risk factors of ACS are: increased age of the US population, the high body mass index (BMI) in a large proportion of the population, and the associated increase in metabolic syndrome.

Aim of work: In this review, we will discuss the most recent evidence regarding Emergent management of patients with acute coronary syndrome

Methodology: We did a systematic search for management of patients with acute coronary syndrome in the emergency department using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles.

Conclusions: ACS is a diagnosis that is made daily in the ED and involve a many diseases ranging from STEMI to low-risk NSTEMI-ACS. ACS diagnosis is based on a group of clinical symptoms, cardiac biomarkers, and ECG findings. Management of ACS is aimed at ending the ischemia of the heart and keeping coronary blood flow balanced. The treatment, vary from fibrinolytic agents and initial PCI on the one hand to conservative and supportive therapy on the other, is proportional with the severity of disease and the chance to improve short-term morbidity and mortality.

Key words: Acute coronary syndrome, diagnosis, management, emergency medicine.

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Please cite this article in press Mesfer Saad Alqahtani et al., *Emergent Management of Patients with Acute Coronary Syndrome.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(11).

INTRODUCTION:

Unstable angina (UA), non-ST segment elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) and ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), are all different forms of myocardial ischemia, and are included in the term: Acute coronary syndrome (ACS).

Nearly 1.3 million of hospital admissions in the US per year are for ACS [1]. The risk factors of ACS are : increased age of the US population, the high body mass index (BMI) in a large proportion of the population, and the associated increase in metabolic syndrome. The increasing of these risk factors means that the number of people at risk for ACS will continue increasing for the near future [2]. This article reviews the current evidence and guidelines for the treatment of patients along the continuum of ACS.

In this review, we will discuss the most recent evidence regarding Emergent management of patients with acute coronary syndrome

METHODOLOGY:

We did a systematic search for management of patients with acute coronary syndrome in the emergency department using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles.

The terms used in the search were: acute coronary artery disease, chest pain, myocardial infarction, management, and emergency department.

DEFINITIONS

ACS is a myocardial ischemia that causes specific symptoms, electrocardiographic (ECG) changes, and/or biochemical marker. The regular symptoms are chest pain or pressure, and in many cases dyspnea, nausea, or malaise. ECG changes may be seen in ACS are: ST-segment elevations, ST-segment depressions and T-wave inversions. When ECG changes are dynamic—change or evolve over time—this tells us that the possibility of ACS is high [3]. Biomedical markers elevation indicates myocardial necrosis leading to myocardial infarction (MI), the higher the risk of serious morbidity and mortality.

The term “Primary ACS” means that the cause of the acute ischemia is the partial or complete occlusion of a coronary artery. Most of the cases of primary ACS are caused by rupture of an atherosclerotic plaque, leading to the formation of intraluminal thrombus, and either complete or partial occlusion of a coronary

artery. The process of coronary thrombus formation is complex. It starts with the activation of the coagulation cascade and leads to the production of fibrin, which catalyzes the polymerization of fibrinogen into a fibrin mesh. Platelets adhere and become activated via several receptor-mediated pathways (including the thrombin receptor). Activated platelets express fibrinogen receptors, allowing the aggregation of platelets into the thrombus via fibrin cross-links. Occlusion of the coronary artery results of either the thrombus formed directly in the intralumin and reduce the blood flow, or by distal embolization of microthrombi. In Less cases of primary ACS, the occlusion caused by coronary artery spasm, coronary artery dissection, and coronary artery thromboembolism.

The term secondary ACS means that the anatomy of the coronary arteries is normal and the cause of myocardial ischemia is caused by pathophysiological mechanisms that limits myocardial oxygen supply like: Hypotension, hypoxemia and severe anemia. And give the same symptoms and signs of the coronary ischemia (primary ACS).

In addition to the supply deficiency, there is another mechanism makes secondary ACS is more likely in patients with underlying coronary artery disease, demand increasing conditions like uncontrolled hypertension or tachycardia can create myocardial energy imbalance and lead to ischemia or injury. Management of secondary ACS focuses on correcting the underlying cause (hypovolemia, hypertensive crisis...etc) and keep the supply-demand balanced. In the other hand, primary ACS management focuses on the coronary thrombus.

About one-third of all cases of acute myocardial ischemia are ST-segment elevation MI (STEMI), based on 2007 estimates and it can be diagnosed by only ECG. STEMI criteria identifies a subset of ACS patients that get better with rapid coronary reperfusion therapy [4], that is why, all the patients that come to the emergency department (ED) with symptoms of STEMI should have an ECG done within 10 minutes of arrival [5].

When ECG changes do not meet the criteria for STEMI, the case called non-ST-segment elevation acute coronary syndrome (NSTEMI-ACS). There are two types of (NSTEMI-ACS): non-ST elevation MI (NSTEMI) and UA. NSTEMI is diagnosed when biomarkers for myonecrosis are positive. Unstable angina (UA) is diagnosed when biomarkers for myonecrosis are negative. From a clinical standpoint, without the examination of cardiac biomarkers for

myonecrosis (it may be late several hours before becoming positive), a distinction between UA and NSTEMI cannot be done.

There are other non-ischemic causes of myocardial necrosis that cause myocardial cell death and biomarker elevation such as acute myocarditis, , chronic Cardiomyopathies, blunt trauma, sepsis, and drug toxicity.

INITIAL TREATMENT

The main aim of treatment of all types of ACS is similar:

1. Balance the supply-demand of the heart.
2. Reduce the formation of the thrombi: antiplatelet and anticoagulant therapies
3. Restore lumen patency: stent placement, angioplasty, and coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG).

It is very important to identify STEMI from other NSTEMI-ACS, to treat early because delaying the treatment of STEMI will cause irreversible transmural damage.

Antiplatelet Therapy

Receiving aspirin as soon as the symptoms start is very important, hence all patients who are suspected having ACS should receive 162 to 325 mg of aspirin directly. Aspirin limits the production of thromboxane via the cyclooxygenase pathway leading to block platelet activation. Aspirin alone can reduce the mortality near 25% in the absence of reperfusion therapy [6]. For rapid absorption and great efficacy, aspirin is recommended to be chewed. Aspirin can be administered via rectal suppository with an adjusted dose range of 300 to 600 mg (Peak serum levels are reached within 90 minutes with rectal dosing), when it can't be taken orally (Peak serum levels are reached within 30 minutes with oral dosing) [7]. The alternative of aspirin when patient allergic to it, is clopidogrel. The recommended dose is 300 to 600 mg [8].

Oxygen

Oxygen is routinely given for all ACS patient within the first 6 hours of presentation[1,12], although, if their oxygen saturation is normal, the carrying capacity of their blood hemoglobin and soluble serum oxygen concentration is only minimally affected by increased concentrations of inhaled oxygen.

Nitroglycerin

Nitroglycerin (NTG) is the initial therapy for chest pain due to ACS. But, administration of nitrates

confers no demonstrated survival benefit with NSTEMI-ACS [9] or with STEMI in the context of current reperfusion intervention [10]. The dose is 0.4 mg sublingual NTG every 5 minutes, or a continuous intravenous infusion of NTG at a dose of 10 to 50 mg/min. NTG reduces the preload, so in case that the patient have critical aortic stenosis NTG is contraindicated. NTG should be used carefully in patients suspected of having right ventricular acute MI.

Nitrates are also contraindicated in patients who have used sildenafil within 24 hours (or up to 72 hours with longer-acting phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitors).

Morphine

Morphine is used when NTG cannot reduce the chest pain or it is contraindicated [1].

Retrospective data suggest higher morbidity among NSTEMI-ACS patients receiving morphine [11] but a causal link is far from established.

b-Blockers

Studies have shown that giving b-blockers to patients with STEMI can reduce the probability of recurrent ischemia and reinfarction after reperfusion therapy.¹² But, different studies showed that the routine administration of b-blockers to STEMI patient may increase the risk of cardiogenic shock and exceed the benefits. So routine intravenous administration of b-blocker for the patient with acute STEMI is not recommended by Current guidelines [13]. But, oral administration of b-blockers for NSTEMI-ACS patients is recommended to be started within 24 hours of presentation.

B-blocker is forbidden whenever the patient have signs of low cardiac output, congestive heart failure, and the other relative contraindications to b-blocker such as asthma, second or third degree heart block, reactive air way disease, or PR interval > 0.24 seconds.

ST-ELEVATION MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

It is very important to start reperfusion strategy as early as possible. It is generally accepted that all else being equal, primary PCI is better than fibrinolytic therapy, in terms of both success in establishing reperfusion and reducing the risk of bleeding. The choice between fibrinolytic therapy and PCI based on the availability of PCI, so if primary PCI is not available within 90 minutes of patient admission, fibrinolytic therapy should be considered [14]. The option to perform fibrinolytic therapy should only occur after consideration of any contraindications,

and should also keep in mind the duration of symptoms. Fibrinolysis has been shown to have very little improvement when started after 3 hours from symptom appearance [15,16]. If a patient is not at a PCI-eligible facility, transfer should be arranged within the 90 minute door-to-needle time frame.

Once the decision is made to perform PCI, the selection and timing of anticoagulation and antiplatelet adjuncts should be discussed with the receiving interventional cardiologist. For patients receiving fibrinolysis the choices for adjunctive therapy are outlined below.

Facilitated PCI

The early administration of fibrinolytics has been hypothesized that will “simplify” the success of eventual PCI. In fact, some studies that examined the use of full-dose fibrinolytics have shown increased rate of complications and morbidity.¹⁷ Partial-dose fibrinolytics with the combinations of glycoprotein IIb/IIIa (GPIIb/IIIa) inhibitors and high-dose heparin have shown no improvement in results and in some cases the risk of bleeding have increased. [14-18]. Current guidelines do not recommend the administration of full-dose fibrinolytics in the patient with STEMI. But, in patient with moderate to high-risk for whom PCI is the perfect strategy, and who have taken long time to arrive to emergency department but PCI can be done within 2 hours, administration of partial-dose fibrinolytics can be discussed with the receiving interventional cardiologist [14].

As the fibrinolysis can cause hemorrhage, the patient should be screened for life-threatening hemorrhage risk. If fibrinolysis is set as initial therapy. The most serious complication of fibrinolytic therapy is the development of intracranial hemorrhage (ICH), which occurs with an incidence of 0.6% to 1% [19] and with a rate of mortality about 50%.²⁵ Old age and uncontrolled hypertension are risk factors for ICH that is associated with fibrinolytic therapy.

Food and Drug Administration have approved four fibrinolytic agents for the treatment of STEMI. The choice of specific agent can vary from an institution to another. Streptokinase, the first fibrinolytic, is not available anymore in many institutions because it is associated with the risk of the formation of antibody and an immune reaction with exposure or reexposure to the drug the features of the different agents are compared as shown:

Follow-Up PCI

Routine PCI directly after fibrinolytic therapy has not

been shown to improve outcomes [20]. In the other hand, coronary perfusion after fibrinolytic administration may be insufficient in about 30% of cases, this appears in continual ischemic symptoms, hemodynamic instability, failure of the resolution of ST-segment, or refractory electrical arrhythmias, and there is proven advantage to PCI in such cases. An observation for 90 minutes is recommended, at which point rescue PCI should be considered. It is also preferred to routinely transfer the patient to a PCI center after fibrinolytic therapy, in order to simplify rescue PCI when required.

Thienopyridines

Thienopyridines are antiplatelet drugs contain clopidogrel and prasugrel and ticagrelor. These agents block the adenosine dihydrophosphate receptors, hence, prevent platelet activation. The only one known to bind reversibly is ticagrelor, but there is not enough studies that experience it in the ED. The best studied one is clopidogrel and it is the only one currently confirmed for administration with fibrinolytic, but it needs the longest time to reach maximal effect. In order to set off this, overriding the loading doses of 300 mg may be recommended, but we should be careful in elderly patients receiving fibrinolytic therapy. Prasugrel may be the alternative choice for patients undergoing PCI with a loading dose of 60 mg, but, patients who had suffered from cerebrovascular disease previously have a higher risk of developing stroke so they should not receive prasugrel.

GPIIb/IIIa Inhibitors

GPIIb/IIIa Inhibitors are intravenous antiplatelet drugs, which contain abciximab, tirofiban, and eptifibatid, they block platelet aggregation by binding to the fibrinogen receptor. The rule is to administer a GPIIb/IIIa inhibitor at or around the time of primary PCI; but, it has not been shown an improvement when used before transfer to the catheterization laboratory. GPIIb/IIIa inhibitors are not effective in the ED for patients in whom a fibrinolytic strategy is chosen.

Anticoagulants

For patients whom we selected PCI as initial therapy, acceptable choices for adjuvant anticoagulation therapy contain unfractionated heparin (UFH), enoxaparin, or bivalirudin. Unfractionated heparin is considered to be among the most widely prescribed agent, and the dose depends on the patient's weight. Bivalirudin is a good choice for PCI because in addition to its efficacy as an anticoagulant it can also avoid the need for GPIIb/IIIa inhibitors and thereby reduce the risk of hemorrhage. UFH and enoxaparin

are both acceptable options for patients taking fibrinolytic agents. If enoxaparin is selected, in patient under 75 years, an intravenous loading dose of 60 mg should be administered along with the first subcutaneous dose. Fondaparinux is a good choice for patients taking fibrinolytic agents who are at high risk of hemorrhage. No studies examined bivalirudin as an adjunct to fibrinolytic therapy. For a summary of some of the advantages and disadvantages of various anticoagulants.

NON-ST-SEGMENT ELEVATION ACS

The main purpose of treatment for NSTEMI-ACS patients is to stabilize the partially occlusive thrombus to reduce the ischemia, and minimize the risk of developing STEMI. There is no known role for fibrinolytic therapy, but PCI is increasingly used to avoid recurrent ischemia. In moderate to high-risk cases, 30-day outcomes are improved when early PCI (within 24–72 hours) is done. The exact timing of PCI in NSTEMI-ACS depends, among other things, on the existence of outstanding or recurrent ischemia or other cardiovascular morbidity. Risk scores like TIMI (Thrombolysis in Myocardial Infarction) and GRACE (Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events) have been developed to predict short-term outcomes and determine the patients who are most likely to improve after earlier and more aggressive therapy. In the other hand, the decision and timing of adjunctive antiplatelet and anticoagulant agents depends on whether and when PCI is done. High risk patients are those who have refractory anginal pain, and evolving ECG changes, high biomarkers, and any patient who have hemodynamic or electrical instability. In these cases urgent PCI is recommended, and the decision and timing of adjuvant antiplatelet and anticoagulant agents are similar to the case of STEMI with primary PCI.

Patients who have a moderate to high risk score but are stable, PCI should be planned within 24 to 48 hours of arrival. It is not recommended to give the patient a GPIIb/ IIIa inhibitor as routine, due to the high risk of hemorrhage. Except if there is a high doubt that the patient will need urgent CABG, giving clopidogrel before PCI is acceptable, and either enoxaparin or heparin can be started in the ED. If, suddenly, the patient becomes unstable, a GPIIb/IIIa inhibitor may be added when the plan for urgent PCI is made. For patients who are at low risk and in whom a no invasive therapy is planned, clopidogrel should still be administered, and enoxaparin is preferred as an anticoagulant. In patients with high risk of hemorrhage, fondaparinux is a reasonable alternate.

CONCLUSIONS:

ACS is a diagnosis that is made daily in the ED and involve a many diseases ranging from STEMI to low-risk NSTEMI-ACS. ACS diagnosis is based on a group of clinical symptoms, cardiac biomarkers, and ECG findings. Management of ACS is aimed at ending the ischemia of the heart and keeping coronary blood flow balanced. The treatment, vary from fibrinolytic agents and initial PCI on the one hand to conservative and supportive therapy on the other, is proportional with the severity of disease and the chance to improve short-term morbidity and mortality.

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